

Oxovanadyl(IV) complexes of 4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazide and 1- α -furyl-4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : Oxovanadyl(IV) complexes of 4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) and 1- α -furyl-4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazone (FBTS) have been prepared. The chemical analyses of the complexes correspond to the general formula $\text{VO}(\text{L})_2\text{Cl}_2$, where L = BTSC and FBTS.

Keywords : Oxovanadyl(IV), thiosemicarbazone, complex.

Introduction

The transition metal complexes of semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazones are interesting due to their biological and medicinal, antitumor, antibacterial and antifungal activity¹⁻⁷. In continuation of our earlier studies⁸⁻¹⁰, we report herein preparation of oxovanadyl(IV) complexes of 4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) and 1- α -furyl-4-benzylamidothiosemicarbazone (FBTS).

Experimental

Material and methods :

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and all the solvents were purified by standard procedures, wherever required. Ligands were prepared as earlier¹¹.

Preparation of the complexes :

25 ml of 1.0 mmol ethanolic solution of oxovanadyl(IV) chloride were mixed with 60 ml of an equimolar ethanolic solutions of the ligands. A deep blue colour was found to develop at pH \sim 3.5 which later changed to bluish green. After concentrating on water-bath, muddy green coloured precipitates were obtained. These were treated with ethanol and ether to exclude the excess of the ligands and were dried in vacuum desiccator. Found: C, 36.98; H, 4.01; N, 19.34; Cl, 12.19; M, 8.75. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_8\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{V}$: C, 36.87; H, 4.10; N, 19.12; Cl, 12.10; V, 8.70%. Found : C, 45.43; H, 3.68; N, 15.03; Cl, 9.81; V, 6.78. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{O}_5\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{V}$: C, 45.29; H, 3.77; N, 15.10; Cl, 9.56; V, 6.87%.

The complexes did not decompose upto 300 °C and were found to be sparingly soluble in ethanol, ether, acetone but soluble in DMF. The vanadium metal was estimated by EDTA using Erichrome black-T as indicator. The analyses of the complexes correspond to general formula $\text{VO}(\text{L})_2\text{Cl}_2$, where L = BTSC and FBTS were carried out by standard literature procedures¹².

Results and discussion

The conductance data in DMF reveal that all the complexes are uni-univalent electrolyte¹³. Analyses show 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The magnetic moments have been found to be normal (1.74 and 1.72 B.M.) at room temperature. As a representative complex $[\text{VO}(\text{BTSC})_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ was subjected to low temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements.

The assignments are made following the scheme suggested by Lever¹⁴. Three bands are expected in the range 11500-13500 cm^{-1} (I), 15000-17000 cm^{-1} (II) and 18000-25500 cm^{-1} (III) and are assignable to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} ; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$.

The value of $10 Dq$ can be obtained directly from the transition ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$. The tetragonal radial parameters, Dt and Ds have been evaluated using the equations suggested by Ballhausen¹⁵. The value of Dt is negative because of the weak σ -donating ability but still greater than π donating ability since both Dq and Ds are positive.

The vanadium-oxygen stretching of frequency in the

IR spectra of complexes appears at 970 cm^{-1} (BTSC) and 965 cm^{-1} (FBTS). The bands are sharp and are in the region expected for V=O stretching frequencies¹⁶.

The far IR spectral bands of the ligands are practically unchanged in these complexes but show new bands at the 552 cm^{-1} and 432 cm^{-1} in BTSC complex and 498 cm^{-1} and 428 cm^{-1} in FBTS complex which have been tentatively assigned^{17,18} to vanadium-nitrogen and vanadium-sulphur vibrations, respectively. The bands at 378 cm^{-1} and 285 cm^{-1} in case of BTSC complex and 372 cm^{-1} and 290 cm^{-1} in case of FBTS complex have been observed in far IR spectra which may be due to symmetric and asymmetric vanadium-chlorine vibration modes, respectively^{19,20}.

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